

ABOUT THE WORDS ADOPTED FROM THE FRENCH LANGUAGE INTO THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Ruziyeva Nasiba Kenjayevna

Head of the Department of Humanities, Kattakorgan Branch of Samarkand State University,
Faculty of pedagogy and language teaching

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Abstract. *Pronunciation of words derived from foreign languages. First of all, it should be mentioned that words borrowed from Uzbek to another languages, such as Russian, Arabic or Persian, do not have their original Uzbek pronunciation, but their pronunciations are adapted to the pronunciation standards of those languages. For example, the Uzbek words, “oqsaqol”, “qarovul”, “tog'a” are pronounced in Tajik as “aksaqol”, “karovul”, “tago”, or the Uzbek words “tanga”, “qishloq”, “o'rik” are pronounced as “dengi”, “kishlak”, “uryuk” in Russian. Signs of becoming dependent on the pronunciation norms of other languages, in particular, English, is appearing without getting rid of the dominance of the Russian pronunciation in our mother tongue established in the Soviet era.*

Keywords: *announcement, address, album, questionnaire, luggage, replica, situation, etc.*

We know that the Uzbek people have interacted with various peoples throughout the historical period. These contacts had a certain influence on the Uzbek language. As a result of interaction, the vocabulary of the Uzbek language has increased due to economic, political, and cultural relations. For example: assimilation of their international words into the Uzbek language under the influence of many peoples (Iran, Macedonia, Hephthalites, Turkic Khanate) who invaded our country in the period up to the VII century (words borrowed from one language to another) past word) and led to its practical use among the population. The period after the 7th century was the time when the Arabs invaded and ruled our country, which led to the influence of the Arabic language on our language and the acquisition of new words. From the 2nd half of the 19th century, due to the transformation of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, into a colonial country of Tsarist Russia, the influence of the Russian language on the Uzbek language and many other European languages (French, Italian, German, English, Spanish) through the Russian language. The introduction of words from the Russian language to the Uzbek language includes two historical periods:

1. The period from the second half of the 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century.
2. The period after 1917.

The Russian language was assimilated into the Uzbek language mainly through two ways: oral (the communication process of various professionals with the local population) and written (the process of correspondence with newspapers, magazines, books, letters). G.V. According to Kolshansky, language works simultaneously as a product of the mental activity of a person and as a form of this activity, and its existence should be based on the compatibility (sufficiency) of the reflected objective reality with the mental language process. The great French philosopher and writer V. Hugo says about the French language: "The French language is not a static language and it will never be." No tongue is frozen, tongues are tossed like the sea." [1]

In linguistics, in particular, in etymology, lexicology and comparative linguistics, the term "borrowing" defines the process for a language to introduce a term from another language into its

lexicon. A possessive word can be direct or indirect. Along with neologism and derivation, a loanword is one of the tools for speakers to increase their lexicon. A loanword changes from one language to another due to certain socio-historical events, trade and cultural contacts.[2] French, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Romanian, Moldovan languages belonging to the group of Romance languages, the common ancestor of all these languages is the Latin language. In the years 58-51 BC, the territory of Gaul, present-day France, was inhabited by Gauls, Franks, Celtic tribes and was conquered by the troops of Julius Caesar and included in the Great Roman Empire. Along with the conquest of Gaul, the culture, language, traditions, and social status of Rome, which was much higher than itself, entered. Thus, as a result of the interaction of the Latin language with the local language, the French language was born. This process lasted for a long time, about 12 centuries. One of the first texts written in ancient Old French is the famous "Song of Roland", which was written in the 12th century. It differs greatly from modern French in its analytical structure, prepositions, word order, and complex verb forms.

The French government considers an active language to be an important support in international politics among the countries of the world in the preservation of language and culture. The President of France created the High Council of Francophonie, which determines the language policy of France. There is a French Language General Commission, which implements the government's language policy, and an advisory committee on the French language. There are even laws on the writing of annotations in French on goods entering the French market from abroad. It is also available. Every year, a list of French equivalents of foreign words is published, which enter France with new technologies, goods, etc. For example, the words computer- instead of ordinateur, software- instead of logiciel, logiciel, software- savoir-faire entered. A law prohibiting the use of foreign words is being discussed. At the initiative of France, there are a number of organizations called to carry out interstate linguistic and cultural work. These are the conferences of heads of state and heads of government of French-speaking countries, which have been held regularly since 1986 by the agency for cultural and technical cooperation. This annual summit brings together and defines the political and cultural cooperation programs of the 58 heads of state.

In 2005, the Francophonie Ministerial Conference in Antananarivo adopted a new Statute of the Organization of La Francophonie, according to which the Agency of La Francophonie was named the International Organization of La Francophonie (OIF). The OIF currently includes 58 member states, Europe, America, the Caribbean, Asia-Pacific, Africa, and the Middle East. The organization has four permanent offices: the African Union and the African Economic Commission in Addis Ababa, the European Union in Brussels, and the United Nations in New York and Geneva.

The relations between Russia and France have many centuries of tradition. The 11th century, when Anna, the daughter of Prince of Kiev Yaroslav the Wise, became the wife of the French king Henry I, the emergence of language relations between these two countries also belongs to this period. The first French-Russian dictionary was compiled by J. Margeret, which was created in France in 1586. For the first time, diplomatic relations between Russia and France were established in 1717, when the first Russian ambassador handed over the credentials signed by Peter I. At different times, many words related to various fields of life entered the Russian language from the French language, and in turn from the Russian language into the Uzbek language (scientific terminology, philosophy, diplomacy, politics, military service, cooking, music, etc.)) For example, diplomatic and economic terms such as diplomacy, consulate, immunity, forum,

commission, bank, advance, credit, check, etc. are derived from the French language finance, acceptance, certificate, capital, accounting, holding, tranche.

"People create their language as a tool for human activity," writes Humboldt. Although individual sounds, grammatical units, phonetic rules, and even contractions can be transferred from one language to another, vocabulary is the main source of loanwords. Certain conditions are necessary to transfer lexical material from one language to another. First of all, long-term language contact between two or more peoples, the presence of bilingual people who know both languages well, as well as the functional necessity of using native words is required. There are different methods of acquiring a foreign word from the donor language to the recipient language: first, through the speech communication of neighboring peoples; secondly, through cultural values, as well as through long-distance connections due to the exchange of scientific information [3]

As our language is constantly developing, dictionaries are expanding every year with new terms, words and phrases that connect society with the world and change culturally and spiritually. The vocabulary and vocabulary of a people is a means of reflecting its life. That is why explanatory dictionaries in all languages have become one of the observers of society in their own way. But the pronunciation of words borrowed from foreign languages should be adapted to Uzbek pronunciation standards.

The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language is enriched with new words every year. In order to clarify these aspects of the words, we would like to think about some specific aspects of the words that entered the Uzbek language from the French language through the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, we want to reveal the specific features of the words used in our daily life today: let's get acquainted with their essence:

Announcement[fr. annonce-public information, announcement]¹⁰ Pre-distributed announcement about tour, performance, concert, etc. (87 pages). Poster -[fr-affiche – announcement]¹¹ Performance, concert, etc. An announcement to be posted in visible places (page 117). the whole thing. 2. A group of artists performing as a whole artistic team. 12 (87 pages)

Interact[fr. Entr'acte, entre-between, between + acte-work, action] a break between performance curtains or concert sections.¹³ (88 pages) Shock absorber [fr.amortir- to weaken, soften] A spring-loaded device that softens the impact¹⁴ (80 pages) .Ampere [fr] (taken from the name of the French physicist A. Ampere) Unit of measurement of electric current. 15 (80b) Ammeter [fr] An instrument that measures current. Amplua [fr. emplois- use, position]. Assembly [fr. Assemblée- assembly, meeting] A plenary meeting of the members of some governing bodies or representatives of several countries in international organizations. 17 (110 b). tied knot] 1. Passenger's load, luggage. 2. The place, compartment of road transport where passenger luggage is placed. 3. street. Knowledge, level 18 (131). French baggage is a travel item that carries its belongings on a muzkoy rod. Ball [fr. Ball, baller- to play, dance]¹⁹ (146 b) A big dance party organized for some occasion. French (bal) a dance meeting on the muskoy rod. Showcase [fr. vitrine-window]²⁰(463) In trade establishments, stores , a specially equipped glass box for placing molar, exhibit samples in photo galleries. Doublets [fr. doublet < double – double, doubled, two contributions]. A second copy of something²¹ (page 654). , a phonogram created by adapting the translation of the dialogues to the mouth movements of the characters of the film. Doubler[fr.doubleur-doubler] is one of two people who take turns doing something or can replace each other in the same job²³ (655 b). Subscription[fr.- abonner - to write, to sign]²⁴ (Volume 3,

page 76) In an ideal situation, the language adapts the foreign word to itself. That is why such words are often absorbed into the language. Subscription is one of the same words. originally comes from the French word "abonner" - to sign, to sign; to sign. The words "abonnement" and "subscriber" adopted into the Uzbek language are cognate with "subscription". However, they did not adapt to the language and retained their European appearance.

Replica [fr. replica-opposition, protest] 1. Objection of the party during the trial, 2. Speech of the partner in the stage dialogue²⁵ (Vol. 3, p. 377).

Resource [fr.ressource increasing tool, method; money] 26 (volume 3, 379 pages)

Restaurant [fr. restaurant-refresh by eating, drinking, restorative, re-energize] 27 (volume 3, 379 pages). Kal'ka [fran. calque – copy, imitation]²⁸. 1. A copy of a drawing or picture 1. Paper specially made for printing. A word or other language unit created by partially copying material from a foreign language. .Cognac [fr.Cognac is the name of a town in France] A strong support for driving and long-term storage of grape wine³⁰ (Volume 2 p. 406).Slang [fr. jargon]. A word for a certain group. The way a group of people stands out from the crowd with their speech, the words and phrases they use with their own meaning. 31 (Volume 2, page 74) Intriga [fr. Intrigue-mislead, lead astray]¹. A secret action made for a malicious purpose³² (Volume 2, page 219) Menu[fr. menu] A piece of paper on which food is salted in restaurants, kitchens and cafes, placed on the appropriate tables or visibly placed; Taomnoma³³ (Volume 2, 580 pages) Kamzul [fr. camisole-knee-length sleeveless men's clothing]³⁴(Volume 2, page 307) Knee-length sleeveless men's clothing is called a camisole in French. This word is used with different sound changes in languages such as German, Latvian, Ukrainian, English, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tatar, Bashkir. Linguistics [fr. linguistics]. Knowledge of language, Linguistics 35 (Volume 2, 499 pages). Situation [fr. Situation situation, condition] situation, situation. 35 (Volume 3, page 527). Tire (fr.) is a punctuation mark with a line longer than the hyphen. French (tiree - dash, tირer - pulling, pulling) is a long and universal distance. Above the indicated words are defined by lexicographers with phonetic and etymological views, and linguists with style. In the long historical process, it is possible to talk about the possible places that arise in the scientific relations, international cultural and expansion of the Uzbek language. Nowadays, the words learned from the French language have a great influence on the enrichment of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language.

In conclusion, it should be noted that as our language is constantly developing, dictionaries are expanding every year with new terms, words and expressions that connect society with the world and are culturally and spiritually changing. The vocabulary and vocabulary of a people is a means of reflecting its life. That is why explanatory dictionaries in all languages have become one of the observers of society in their own way. But the pronunciation of words borrowed from foreign languages should be adapted to Uzbek pronunciation standards. In this case, on the one hand, the variants of such words in the colloquial language (for example, gazeta-gazet, doctor-dukhtir, mashina-moshina, moshin v.h), on the other hand, their Uzbek phonetics and pronunciation standards We think that it should be taken into account how it can be pronounced (for example, bus-aptabuz, tractor-tractor, car-car, airport-airport, concept-conception, etc.).

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